

SAEGE

D1.1

Management and Quality Assurance Guidelines

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1. Introduction

About this document

This deliverable sets out the management and quality assurance guidelines governing the implementation of the SAEGE project. Specific guidelines for communication, inclusion, and data management will be addressed in dedicated deliverables.

The guidelines presented in this document aim to:

- Ensure transparent, accountable, and effective project management;
- Safeguard scientific quality, ethical integrity, and independence;
- Enable inclusive and pluralistic engagement with experts and stakeholders;
- Promote responsible use of artificial intelligence (AI);
- Support continuous learning and improvement throughout the project lifecycle.

These guidelines constitute a living framework and will be reviewed and updated throughout the project to reflect lessons learned through collaboration with the European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies (EGE) and its Secretariat, as well as wider developments in scholarship and best practice for policy advice.

About SAEGE

SAEGE is a project funded by the EU under Horizon Europe and delivered by EUREC Office, the Office of the European Network of Research Ethics Committees (EUREC). The project runs from November 2025 to October 2029 (48 months). The full project title is *Support for the Activities of the European Group on Ethics (EGE) by European Academia and Ethics Bodies*.

The mission of SAEGE is to support the work of the EGE and to enhance its impact in the following areas:

- **Delivering targeted evidence** of the highest scientific quality in a timely and transparent manner;
- **Network-building** through the creation and maintenance of a Europe-wide, cross-disciplinary ethics network (EGEAN);
- **Horizon scanning** to alert the EGE and the European Commission to emerging issues with ethical or societal relevance;
- **Policy impact and public awareness** through policy engagement, communication, and integration of ethics advice into science advice processes.

SAEGE does not issue ethical opinions, normative conclusions, or policy recommendations. Ethical judgment, value balancing, and final advice remain the sole responsibility of the EGE.

SAEGE is organised into five work packages (WPs):

- **WP1:** Coordination
- **WP2:** Developing evidence-based ethics advice
- **WP3:** Development and coordination of ethics advice network
- **WP4:** Horizon scanning for emerging ethical issues
- **WP5:** Communication and policy engagement

Unlike many Horizon Europe projects, SAEGE adopts a flexible staffing model. WPs 2, 3, and 4 are jointly staffed by a core team, enabling rapid and coherent responses to EGE requests as topics arise. WP5 is delivered by a specialised communications and policy engagement team, while WP1 covers governance, management, and administrative functions.

2. Project Management, Governance, and Coordination

Overall management and coordination approach

SAEGE is implemented as a single-beneficiary Horizon Europe project within EUREC Office, which holds full scientific, administrative, financial, and ethical responsibility for the project. This structure enables coherent governance, consistent ethical standards, and clear accountability in supporting the EGE and the EGE Secretariat / European Commission Unit in Charge.

Project management and coordination are designed as an integrated system, combining formal governance structures with flexible internal and external communication practices suited to the advisory, on-demand nature of SAEGE's work. This integrated approach ensures effective coordination of activities, compliance with Horizon Europe requirements, and the timely delivery of high-quality outputs.

While SAEGE does not involve formal project partners, it collaborates closely with members of relevant networks, with experts and other relevant stakeholders. These actors contribute on a consultative or operational basis, while decision-making authority and overall responsibility remain with EUREC Office.

Overall coordination is ensured through Task 1.1 (Project coordination and liaison with the EC Unit in charge), which covers administrative, financial, operational, and coordination activities throughout the project duration

EUREC Office is responsible for:

- Coordinating all project activities and timelines;
- Managing the project budget and financial reporting;
- Ensuring compliance with Horizon Europe rules, contractual obligations, and reporting requirements;
- Overseeing agreements with budgeted cooperators and experts;
- Maintaining regular communication with the EGE Secretariat and the EC Unit in charge.

Governance and coordination meetings

Management Board Meetings

A Management Board is established comprising representatives from:

- SAEGE;
- The EGE Secretariat / EC Unit in charge;
- The EU agency responsible for the grant.

The Management Board provides high-level strategic oversight, ensures alignment with EU policy priorities, and facilitates coordination between SAEGE and the EGE. It reviews project progress, discusses strategic orientations, and supports the timely resolution of issues that may affect implementation. Meetings are held at least quarterly, or more frequently if required.

Internal Steering Committee Meetings

An Internal Steering Committee provides guidance on the scientific, ethical, and societal dimensions of the project. It includes representatives from:

- The EUREC network;
- ALLEA;
- YASAS;
- Academia Europaea;
- Other relevant networks connected through the EGE Et Alia Advisory Network (EGEAN).

The committee offers pluralistic perspectives, advises on stakeholder engagement strategies, and contributes to the refinement of methodologies and thematic priorities. It does not hold decision-making authority. Final responsibility for project decisions and outputs remains with EUREC Office. Meetings are held at least quarterly.

EGE Chairs, EGE Secretariat, SAEGE coordination meetings

Monthly meetings with the EGE Chairs, the EGE Secretariat and the SAEGE managing team provide a forum for discussing priorities, emerging issues, and ongoing work. These exchanges support mutual understanding, timely alignment, and effective support to the EGE, while preserving institutional independence and clearly defined roles.

Following coordination meetings, relevant information is shared internally to ensure transparency and integration into ongoing activities.

Internal Communication

Internal communication within SAEGE is guided by the principles of transparency, clarity, responsiveness to advisory needs, inclusiveness, and clear allocation of responsibility. Formal governance mechanisms are complemented by flexible communication practices suited to the evolving and on-demand nature of the project.

Regular internal meetings support coordination, knowledge sharing, and coherence across work packages and tasks. Ad hoc exchanges are used to respond efficiently to emerging requests from the EGE and EGE-Secretariat and to manage interdependencies between activities.

Involvement of external experts, stakeholders and networks

SAEGE collaborates with external experts and networks to support information gathering, analysis, and stakeholder engagement. Such collaboration is governed by clear agreements defining scope of work, ethical and confidentiality obligations, conflict-of-interest management, and data protection requirements.

All external contributions are reviewed and integrated under EUREC Office oversight. External contributors provide input to specific tasks and activities but do not assume responsibility for project governance or final outputs. All contributions are reviewed, assessed, and integrated under EUREC's oversight to ensure consistency with SAEGE's quality assurance and ethical standards.

Engagement with external experts and organisations is:

- Purpose-driven and proportional to the advisory need;
- Transparent regarding the scope and use of contributions;
- Documented in a proportionate and appropriate manner.

External contributors provide input on a consultative basis and do not assume responsibility for project governance or final outputs.

Involving networks

External coordination is structured primarily through the EGE Et Alia Advisory Network (EGEAN), which connects ethics councils, academic experts, advisory bodies, civil society organisations, and affected communities across Europe and beyond.

Involving experts

Depending on the nature, scope, and timelines of a request, SAEGE outputs may be produced by project staff, by one or more selected experts, or by contracted scientific writers, working individually or collaboratively as appropriate. The involvement of experts is designed to ensure scientific quality, independence, and credibility. Potential biases are addressed through careful expert selection; disclosure and assessment of interests; and the use of peer review, internal review, or expert validation. SAEGE seeks to ensure balanced representation of relevant perspectives and transparently documents methodological choices, assumptions, and areas of uncertainty.

Where required, outputs may undergo peer review, expert validation, quality control, editing, proofreading, and/or translation. All outputs will be made available open access in accordance with the Data Management Plan, including through publication on repositories or project websites.

Coordination with SAPEA

In line with Task 3.3, SAEGE establishes regular channels of communication with science advisory organisations at EU level to support the integration of ethics advice and science advice. Priority is given to collaboration with SAPEA, enabling coordination in cases where the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (GCSA) and the EGE provide parallel scientific and ethical advice. Where appropriate, shared procedures or memoranda of understanding may be developed to facilitate coordinated advisory processes.

Documentation, Transparency, and Feedback

Key communication and coordination activities are documented in a proportionate manner to ensure transparency, continuity, and institutional memory.

Feedback from internal staff, external experts, and network members is used to refine communication practices and improve coordination over time. Project implementation is continuously monitored through internal reviews and regular reporting against milestones, deliverables, and indicators. Management processes are adaptive, allowing adjustments in response to emerging ethical challenges, evolving advisory needs, or changes in the policy landscape.

This adaptive approach is supported by:

- Annual updates to management and quality assurance guidelines;
- Ongoing data management oversight in line with the Data Management Plan;
- Continuous attention to inclusion and pluralism;
- Impact monitoring and evaluation activities.

Through this integrated management, governance, and coordination framework, SAEGE ensures transparent oversight, effective communication, and the delivery of high-quality, ethically grounded support to the EGE and EU policymaking processes.

3. Quality assurance

Quality assurance within SAEGE is designed to ensure that all outputs meet the **highest scientific and ethical standards**, in line with the project's objective to provide robust, evidence-based ethics advice to the EGE.

The quality assurance framework is guided by the following core principles:

- **Scientific excellence:** All evidence gathering and analysis are conducted using recognised and appropriate methodologies.
- **Ethical integrity:** Ethical reflection is systematic, transparent, and grounded in established ethics frameworks.
- **Pluralism and inclusiveness:** Diverse perspectives are actively sought and carefully integrated.
- **Policy relevance:** Outputs are tailored to the needs of the EGE and EU policymaking contexts.
- **Transparency and traceability:** Sources, methods, and contributions are clearly documented.

These principles apply across all project activities, including evidence sourcing, ethical analysis, horizon scanning, stakeholder engagement, and output production.

As a single-beneficiary project, SAEGE's quality assurance is centrally coordinated by EUREC, which retains full responsibility for the quality and integrity of all outputs.

Quality assurance is an integral component of SAEGE's support to the EGE and is embedded across all stages of the workflow.

This includes:

- **Clear documentation** of scope, methods, and limitations;
- **Critical review** and contextualisation of external contributions;
- **Conflict-of-interest management** for consulted experts;
- **Internal review of outputs** to ensure coherence, balance, and policy relevance;
- **Transparency** regarding uncertainty, disagreement, and knowledge gaps.

The following guidelines apply to SAEGE staff, contributing experts, science writers, and other contributors involved in SAEGE activities:

- SAEGE ensures that all outputs are based on the **most up-to-date scientific evidence available across all relevant disciplines**.
- Where aligned with the scope of the request, **SAEGE involves external experts with the specific expertise** required for each topic.
- Results are presented in a **scientifically balanced and objective manner**.
- SAEGE follows the **principles of diversity, inclusiveness, and equal participation**, supported by a dedicated inclusion plan.
- When **differences in scientific views** among contributing experts cannot be resolved, these differences are clearly identified and explained in the outputs.
- All contributing experts are required to complete a **Declaration of Interests form**. These declarations are assessed, considered, and published to ensure transparency and independence of advice.
- SAEGE outputs provide **clear documentation of the methods** used to obtain results, sources of funding, and the names and affiliations of all contributors.
- SAEGE adheres to the **FAIR principles** for data management and the principles of Open Science, promoting transparency, accessibility, and reproducibility of outputs.

A quality assurance checklist will be developed to support consistent practices.

4. SAEGE Approach to Supporting the EGE

Purpose and scope

This chapter sets out SAEGE's overall approach to supporting the EGE in the development of its opinions and statements. It defines the nature of SAEGE's support, its methodological principles, and the boundaries between SAEGE's analytical role and the EGE's normative authority. Quality assurance procedures are embedded throughout this approach to ensure that all support provided is rigorous, transparent, inclusive, and fit for purpose.

SAEGE's role is to enable and strengthen the EGE's ethical deliberations by expanding the informational, analytical, and experiential foundations available to EGE members. SAEGE does not formulate ethical conclusions, normative judgments, or policy recommendations. Responsibility for ethical evaluation, value balancing, and final advice rests exclusively with the EGE.

Nature of SAEGE contributions: Ethically relevant information

SAEGE frames its work as the provision of ethically relevant information rather than the production of ethical "evidence" or conclusions. In the context of ethics, conclusions are not established through empirical proof alone but emerge from deliberative processes involving normative reasoning and value judgment.

Accordingly, SAEGE's contributions may include:

- Scientific and technical background relevant to the topic under consideration including a mapping of the main technological developments;;
- Empirical findings on societal impacts, lived experiences, risks, and benefits, where available;
- Analysis of existing policy, legal, regulatory and governance frameworks and trends at EU, national (also non-EU countries) and international levels
- Perspectives and insights from a diverse range of experts, practitioners, stakeholders, and affected communities;
- Identification and articulation of ethical questions, tensions, uncertainties, and areas of disagreement.

Ethics information-gathering workflow

SAEGE follows a structured workflow to translate EGE requests into analytically robust inputs that support ethical deliberation.

Step 1: Request and Scoping

Following the European Commission's scoping process, requests for SAEGE originate from the EGE and its Secretariat and are formalised through a Specification of Work (SoW) that defines the scope, objectives, timelines, and expected outputs. At this stage, SAEGE may provide methodological input to clarify feasibility, comprehensiveness, thoroughness, appropriateness and proportionality, or propose multiple options intended to meet the expressed needs of the EGE and Secretariat. Final decisions regarding framing, prioritisation and options selection remain with the EGE Secretariat.

Step 2: Method Selection and Information Sourcing

Based on the agreed scope and Specification of Work, SAEGE undertakes the information-gathering and analytical work and selects SAEGE outputs appropriate to the topic and timelines. These may include literature and policy reviews, ethical review reports that describe and map the ethical landscape of the topic, synthesising existing ethical analyses, positions, and debates, workshops, interviews, or other formats as appropriate. SAEGE typically operates at a meta-analytical level, synthesising existing research, expertise, and experience, rather than conducting large-scale primary research.

Step 3: Consultation and Inclusiveness

Consultation activities are designed to elicit diverse and relevant perspectives and opinions as well as policy/technological/governance trends or determine what is ethically preferable. Participant selection follows transparent procedures guided by the Inclusion Plan and includes attention to geographic balance (including Widening countries), gender balance, career-stage diversity, and disciplinary and experiential diversity. All participants are subject to conflict-of-interest assessment.

Step 4: Analysis and Synthesis

Upon request, SAEGE analyses and synthesises gathered material, including outputs from consultation activities conducted under Step 3, to identify key ethical issues, relevant values and principles, societal concerns as reflected in the reviewed literature, policy documents, and consultation inputs, and implications of different governance or policy approaches. Where requested, SAEGE may outline policy-relevant options understood as analytically grounded scenarios, but not policy recommendations. ~~These scenarios do not constitute recommendations and do not express normative judgments.~~

Step 5: Outputs and Handover

Outputs vary in format and length depending on scope and timelines. All outputs undergo internal quality assurance, including review for analytical coherence, transparency of methods, and clarity of presentation. Following handover, SAEGE may provide clarification or additional information if requested to ensure alignment with the SoW, but does not participate in the EGE's drafting, validation, or decision-making processes.

Respect for institutional roles and independence

Throughout all support activities, **SAEGE acts with full respect for the EGE's institutional mandate and independence**. External experts and stakeholders engaged through SAEGE provide input on a consultative basis and do not replace or supplant the EGE's authority. SAEGE's work is designed to inform and ground, not to determine, ethical conclusions.

By clarifying roles, embedding quality assurance, and focusing on ethically relevant information, SAEGE strengthens the EGE's capacity to deliver timely, robust, and policy-relevant ethical guidance while preserving the integrity of the EGE's deliberative process.

In addition, SAEGE recognizes the importance of respecting the mandate and responsibilities of the European Commission. Activities are structured to ensure clarity in the allocation of tasks and responsibilities among the Commission, SAEGE, and the EGE. SAEGE's role is strictly supportive, complementing the Commission's policy-making functions and the EGE's deliberative expertise, while ensuring that no overlap undermines the institutional mandates of either body.

5. Ethics and research integrity

SAEGE conducts all activities in full compliance with ethical principles, the highest standards of research integrity, and applicable EU, international, and national law, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms. Particular attention is given to proportionality, privacy, data protection, the physical and mental integrity of persons, non-discrimination, environmental protection, and high levels of human health protection. SAEGE also adheres to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ALLEA).

SAEGE may carry out research that involves humans, such as surveys, Delphi studies, or stakeholder engagement. All relevant procedures involving human participants will be reviewed and approved by institutional ethics committees where required. All human research will comply with GDPR and established ethical standards, ensuring informed and voluntary participation, clear communication on the purpose of the research and data use, proportionality in data collection, and particular care when engaging affected or vulnerable groups.

6. Responsible use of Artificial Intelligence

The responsible use of artificial intelligence (AI) in SAEGE is addressed primarily through Task 2.5, which responds to the growing need for operational guidance on the use of AI in ethics advice by developing procedures and quality controls for AI use within the EGE Et Alia Advisory Network (EGEAN).

Rather than starting from scratch, this work builds on existing European Commission AI Guidelines and other relevant frameworks, reviewing and adapting them to the specific context of ethics advisory processes and the EGEAN network.

Acknowledging the increasing deployment of AI tools across the ethics advisory ecosystem and the associated ethical risks and practical limitations, this work is informed by a review and mapping of existing AI applications within EGEAN and ethics advisory processes across Europe, analysis of related initiatives, including complementary work in the SAPEA project, and limited experimentation with AI research tools by the SAEGE team, notably in the areas of horizon scanning and rapid evidence synthesis.

These activities support the identification of best practices, gaps, and potential risks related to issues such as bias, privacy, and consent, and inform the drafting of guidelines, which are subject to external review by experts within the EGEAN network. Where AI or data aggregation tools are employed in other project activities, including the early alert and horizon-scanning toolbox under Task 4.1, SAEGE applies the same approach as set out in the Description of Action, ensuring transparency and compliance with European legal and ethical best practice.